

Universal “MaxTheMin“ B_1 Shimming: Robust Adiabatic Pulses at Ultra High-field

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Synopsis

Keywords: adiabatic pulses, UHF MRI, calibration-free B_1 shim

Motivation: In ultra high-field MRI, achieving complete magnetization inversion using adiabatic pulses is challenging.

Goal(s): Develop robust calibration-free adiabatic pulses which fulfill the adiabatic condition throughout the entire brain.

Approach: This study investigates a universal “MaxTheMin” B_1 shimming technique, ensuring that the adiabatic condition is satisfied for robust pulse performance. By optimizing the lowest B_1 level, we attain high inversion efficiency, even in regions where B_1 is initially weak. As a practical application, MP2RAGE acquisitions were performed.

Results: Simulations and in vivo experiments confirm that “MaxTheMin” B_1 shimming enhances pulse efficacy at 7T, making it a valuable tool for imaging at ultra-high fields.

Impact: Universal B_1 shimming improves adiabatic pulse performance by enhancing inversion efficiency across the brain without increasing scan time or requiring calibration. This advancement paves the way for higher-quality, more reproducible imaging at UHF, expanding its clinical and research applications.

Introduction

Achieving effective adiabatic pulses is essential for high-field MRI, where fulfilling the adiabatic condition across the brain can be challenging [1,2,3]. This study introduces universal “MaxTheMin” B_1 shimming [4] as a calibration-free approach to increase the minimum B_1 field, ensuring robust adiabatic inversion and addressing regions with initially low B_1 . By removing the requirement for calibration scans, this method saves valuable scan time and can be applied consistently across different subjects. Simulations and in vivo studies confirm that this shimming strategy enhances pulse efficacy by reliably meeting the adiabatic condition, offering a practical solution for improving imaging quality at ultra high-field.

Methods

A database of B_0 and B_1 maps from 20 healthy adults was utilized to compute the complex shim weights for each transmit coil element. The optimization was initialized in CP-mode, with a boundary condition ensuring that the total pulse power remains constant.

To meet the adiabatic condition during inversion across the entire brain, the cost function was designed to maximize the minimum B_1 field.

Unlike general pulse optimization, which focuses on field homogenization, adiabatic pulses only require a sufficient minimum B_1 field to achieve complete magnetization inversion. The stretched hyperbolic secant (HS_n) implementation is based on the work of Tesiram et al. [5], using the following pulse parameters: 10.24 ms duration, 2 kHz bandwidth, HS_n exponent = 7, peak B_1 amplitude = 0.372 kHz (8.74 uT) x 2 (power scale), 99% desired inversion efficiency, and 10% maximum inversion error.

All experiments were performed with a MAGNETOM 7T Plus scanner (Siemens Healthcare, Erlangen, Germany) using a head array coil with 32 receive and 8 transmit channels (Nova Medical, Wilmington, USA). In vivo experiments were performed in accordance with guidelines set by the institutional review board. Whole-head 3D-DREAM B_1 maps [6] and whole-head MP2RAGE [7] images were acquired using both CP-mode and universal B_1 shim.

DREAM parameters: 5 mm isotropic resolution, FoV = 220x220x200 mm³, TR/TE = 3000/2.33 ms, nominal flip angle = 50°. MP2RAGE parameters: 0.8 mm isotropic resolution, FoV = 230x230x180 mm³, TR/TRgre/TE/TR = 5000/5.6/1.9 [ms], TI1/TI2 = 800/2700 [ms], $\alpha=4.5^\circ/6.5^\circ$, iPAT=4, acquisition time 4:14 min.

Results

The top row of Figure 1 compares simulated B_1 fields between CP-mode and the universal “MaxTheMin” B_1 shim. The bottom row demonstrates that the predicted B_1 fields were accurately replicated in a subject not included in the training database, confirming the method’s robustness. Figures 2 and 3 display MP2RAGE images acquired with and without the universal B_1 shim, illustrating that, with the same pulse energy, applying the shim improves inversion in the cerebellum while maintaining the adiabatic condition elsewhere. Additionally, an acquisition with 10% lower peak power still achieved high inversion efficiency.

Discussion

Universal “MaxTheMin” B_1 shimming achieves robust adiabatic inversion at 7T by focusing on increasing the minimum B_1 field rather than homogenizing it. This approach effectively meets the adiabatic condition necessary for complete magnetization inversion, thereby improving image quality without re-

quiring time-consuming calibration scans. The in vivo results confirm that the universal shim maintains inversion efficiency across the brain, particularly addressing limitations in the cerebellum where incomplete inversion often occurs. Furthermore, the ability to sustain inversion efficiency even with reduced peak power highlights the method’s potential to lower patient RF exposure.

Conclusion

The “MaxTheMin” B_1 shimming approach provides an effective and calibration-free solution to enhance adiabatic pulse efficacy at 7T. It ensures consistent magnetization inversion, addressing limitations in regions like the cerebellum. This method offers a practical and time-saving enhancement for ultra-high field MRI.

References

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Figures

Figure 1

Top: Simulated B_1 maps in quadrature (CP) mode (left) and with the universal B_1 shim applied (right), generated from a database subject. The shim effectively boosts the B_1 field in low-field regions while slightly reducing it in high-field areas, thereby maintaining an overall high B_1 field. Bottom: Acquired B_1 maps, rescaled to match the B_1 field of the adiabatic pulse. The measured field distribution closely aligns with the simulations, confirming the predictive accuracy of the universal B_1 shim.

Figure 2

MP2RAGE acquisitions illustrate HSn inversion in CP-mode (left) and with the universal B₁ shim (middle). The right panel shows the HSn inversion with a 10% reduction in peak power using the universal B₁ shim. In CP-mode, the adiabatic condition is violated, leading to incomplete inversion in the cerebellum, as evidenced by signal brightening and contrast loss. The universal B₁ shim addresses this issue, achieving complete inversion in the cerebellum even with reduced peak power.

Figure 3

This zoomed-in view of the cerebellum highlights the inversion efficiency differences. The left panel shows incomplete inversion in CP-mode, characterized by signal brightening and contrast loss due to the violation of the adiabatic condition. In contrast, the middle panel demonstrates the effectiveness of the universal B₁ shim, achieving complete inversion. The right panel illustrates that even with a 10% reduction in peak power, the universal B₁ shim maintains high inversion efficiency, emphasizing its ability to enhance performance in challenging anatomical regions.